

A f73v, line 4; B f65r, line 4, (Png o66.tif); C f37r, line 7.

piṅgalovāca

- 9.1 gr̥havāstuḥ sureśena sūcito noditas tvayā
nāḍīnāṃ ca vibhāgo 'pi avayavānāṃ ca sūladhṛk
- 9.2ab etat sarvaṃ samāsenā kathyatāṃ śaśīśekhara
bhairava uvāca
- 9.2cd caturaśrīkṛte kṣetre gr̥harūpo 'thavā priye
- 9.3 daśanāḍīr vibhajyādaḥ sūtrapātaṃ tu kārayet
nāḍīnāṃ tu yathā saṃkhyā saṃjñābhir nigadāmi te
- 9.4 śāntā yaśovatī kāntā viśālā prāṇavāhiṇī
satī ca sumatī nandā subhadrā ca manoramā
- 9.5 daśanāḍyaḥ smṛtā hy etāḥ pratyakprācīmukhodgatāḥ
hiraṇyā suprabhā lakṣmī vibhūtir vimalā śriyā
- 9.6 jayā jvālā viśokā ca śubhā caivottarāmukhāḥ
pratyag daśabhir nāḍībhiḥ śubho jñeyo dharātmajāḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

before 1 piṅgalovāca] BC; piṅgalaüvāca A

1a vāstuḥ] BC; vāstu A • sureśena] em.; sureśāna ABC

1b tvayā] BC; tvayāḥ A

1d avayavānāṃ] A.; avayavā{nāṃ} C; avayavāñ B

2a sarvaṃ] BC; sarva A

3a nāḍīr] A; nāḍī BC 3b pātaṃ] em.; pātraṃ AC; pātran B

3d saṃjñābhir nigadāmi] em.; saṃkhyābhirnigadāmi A; saṃjñābhirnadadāmi BC

4a śāntā yaśovatī] em.; sāntāyasovatī A; sāntayesovatī B; sāntayesovatī C

4c satī] A; sātī BC

4d subhadrā ca] A; subhadrā[-] C; subhadrā B • manoramā] BC; manoramāḥ A

5c hiraṇyā] BC; hi[[ra]]raṇyā A • lakṣmī] AB; lakṣmīr C

5d vibhūtir] A; vibhūtiḥ C; vibhūti B 6c daśabhir] C; daśabhiḥr A; daśabhi B

• nāḍībhiḥ] em.; nāḍībhi ABC6d jñeyo] BC; jñeyā A

- 9.7 devatānāṃ yathā nyāsas tathā samyañ nibodha me
nābhau navapade brahmā āpas tadīśasamsthitaḥ
- 9.8 dvipade tu sa boddhavyas tadvad vatsas tadīśataḥ
brahmāgneye tu savitā sāvitri tasya pāvake
- 9.9 dvipadau tau vijānīyāt keticendraḥ pade tu saḥ
tasyāpītidīśābhāge jayendro dvipadasthitaḥ A f74r
- 9.10 brahmātiryago rudras tu rudradāsas tathaiva ca
dvipadau tau vijānīyāt kapūrve ṣaṇmarīcikaḥ B f65v
- 9.11 vivasvān ṣaḍpadāvasthaṃ bhavayāmye vidur budhāḥ
padmayonyāpago bhadre ṛtvavasthaḥ kalādhīpaḥ
- 9.12 ātmabhuvottare nyasya ṣaḍpade tu dharādharā
vatseśe īśaṃ vinyasya parjanyaś tadanantaram

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

7a nyāsas] AC; nyāśaḥ B 7b samyañ] C; samyan AB

8c brahmāgneye] A; brahmāgne BC

9b cendraḥ] em.; cendra AB; caṇdra C • saḥ] em.; sā BC; śā A

9c tasyāpīti] AC; tasyāpīti B 9d jayendro] em.; jayendra ABC

10a tiryago] em.; tiryaga ABC 10b rudradāsas] A; rudrāsas B; rudrāsaptas C

10c tau] AC; to B 11a ṣaḍ] AB; pad C 11b yāmye] AB; yāme C

11c āpago] BC; āpaso A

12b dharādharā] A; dharādharā B; dharādharāḥ C

12c vatseśe] em.; vaccheśe A; vacchese B; vakṣese C

- 9.13 jayo mahendrasūryas tu satyo bhṛśas tathaiva ca
antarikṣas tu vijñeyāḥ padikāḥ pañktisaṃsthitāḥ
- 9.14 sāvītryā pāvake 'gnis tu pūṣā vitatham eva ca
gṛhakṣato yamaś caiva gandharvo bhṛṅgakaṃ nyaset
- 9.15 mṛgaś ca padikā jñeyā yāmyapañktivavasthitāḥ
jayād ityaṃśake pitṛdauvāris tadanantaram
- 9.16 sugrīvaḥ puṣpadantas tu pracetasas tathaiva ca
asuraḥ śoṣarogaś ca padikāḥ paścime matāḥ
- 9.17 rudradāsaś ca vāyavyaṃ vāyuṃ caiva tu vinyaset
nāgamukhyas tu bhalvāṭasomo rigis tathaiva ca
- 9.18ab aditir ditināmā ca padikāś cottare gatāḥ

C f37v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

13a mahendra] em.; māhendra ABC

14a pāvake 'gnis] C; vakegnis B; pāvakognis A

14d gandharvo] em.; gāndharvo ABC

15b yāmya] BC; yāmyaṃ A • pañkti] AC; pakti B

15c ity] AB; ity C 15d dauvāris] em.; dvauvāris ABC

18a aditir ditināmā] BC; aditināmā A 18b gatāḥ] A; gatā BC

- 9.18cd carakī ca vidārī ca pūtanā pāparākṣasī
- 9.19 īsakoṇāditaḥ kṛtvā yāvad ante prabhañjanaḥ
skando 'ryamātha jambhaś ca pilipicchas tathaiva ca
- 9.20 pūrvādy athottarānte tu nyastavyās tu sulocane
dharāsamdhāraṇārthe tu gīrvāṇāny anyathā sthitiḥ
- 9.21 vaṃśadvayaṃ yathāpūrvam rajjavo 'ṣṭau tathaiva ca
tripadā kiṃ tu turyas turyānyā ṣaḍpadā priye
- 9.22 marmopamarmabhedaś ca yathāpūrvam tathātra tu
anyat marmākulaṃ caiva jñātavyaṃ tu sulocane
- 9.23 kaṃ lalāṭabhruvau karṇau netre ghrāṇasavībukau
oṣṭhe gaṇḍau sagocchā ca dvijau jihvā tathaiva ca
- 9.24 hanuṃ garuḍakūpaś ca sa kaṇṭhaś ca vijānataḥ
skandho bāhū tu vijñeye kurparau tu tathaiva ca

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 19a īsakoṇāditaḥ] AC; īsakoṇādita B
19c skando 'ryamātha] AB; skandhoyamotha C
19d pilipicchas] BC; pilipicchaṃ A
20c dharā] AB; parī C 20d gīrvāṇāny anyathā] A; gīrvāṇāṃnyanyathā BC
21c turyas] AB; tuyas C
23a karṇau] A; varṇṇau BC
23c gocchā ca] conj.; gauñja ABC
24a hanuṃ] AC; hanu B

9.25 śalākāmaṇibandhau tu tale cāṅgulayo nakhāḥ
uro ḥṛc ca stanau pārśvau jaṭharaṃ nābhikukṣikau

9.26 kaṭisphicau tathā śiśnavṛṣaṇau muṣkapāyū ca
ūrū jānus tathā jaṅghe gulphau pārṣṇī padau tathā

A f74v

9.27 aṅgulyas tu nakhāḥ pṛṣṭhaṃ mārgahr̥tkakṛkāṭikā
trikaṭena samāyuktaṃ rudramarmādhikaṃ śatam

9.28 īśakoṇe śiras tasya tanmadhye tu bhruvau yadā
tadūrdhve tu lalāṭaṃ syāt samantāt tu vijānataḥ

B f66r

9.29 karṇau tu ditiparjanyau jñātavyau tu sulocane
netre ca bhrūradhobhāge bhrūmadhye bindur ucyate

9.30 bindusaṃgatanāsā ca ghrāṇādhaḥ sandhigaṇḍakau
oṣṭhau gocchā dvijau jihvā vatsasthe saptadhā kṛte

Ω = AB(→C)

25a śalākā] em.; śalākā PI 9.35b; sakāla ABC

• maṇibandhau] AC; maṇibaṇibandhau B

25c uro] AB; ūrvau C 26b muṣkapāyū] A; muṣkakapāyū BC

26d padau] BC; pāda A 27a nakhāḥ] em.; nakhā ABC

27b ḥṛka] A; ḥṛkṣa BC 28c lalāṭaṃ] AC; lalāṭa B

28d samantāt] BC; samaṃtām A

30a bindu] AB; binduṃ C

• saṃgata] B; śaṃgata A; saṃjānta C

30c gocchā] conj.; goṅja AB; gaṇḍau C

- 9.31 adhaś cordhvakrameṇaiva madhye jihvā yathā bhavet
gocchā dvayavibhāge tu adharoṣṭhau tathaiva ca
- 9.32 dvijau bhāgadvaye proktau madhyaikā rasanā bhavet
hanu padāntikaṃ sandhiṃ kaṇṇamūlād vidur budhāḥ
- 9.33 vaktramaṇḍalam etaṃ tu vāstoḥ samyak prakāśitam
garuḍaḥ kaṇṭhakūpaś ca ardhāpye tu tribhāgikāḥ
- 9.34 adho 'rdhāpye tu yat proktam uras tat parikalpayet
jaye skandhas vijānīyān mahendre bāhur ucyate
- 9.35 āditye kurparaṃ jñeyaṃ śalākā bhṛśasatyake
maṇibandho 'ntarīkṣe ca karaṃ caivāgnir eva ca
- 9.36 sāvitraṅguli vijñeyā savitā ca nakhāḥ smṛtāḥ
vāstor vāmaṃ samākhyātaṃ dakṣaṃ so ditir ucyate

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

31c gocchā] conj.; goñja AB; gaṇḍa C

33a vaktra] BC; vaktraṃ A

34a adho 'rdhāpye] AB; adhordhvāpye C

34c skandhas] AB; skaṇḍhaṃ C

34d mahendre] em.; māheṇḍre A; mādendra B; mādendraṃ C

36b ca] C; va AB

• nakhāḥ smṛtāḥ] AB; nakhaḥsmṛtaḥ C 36c vāmaṃ] A; vāma BC

36d dakṣaṃ] BC; daṃkṣiṃ A

- 9.37 rigisthāne bhujam jñeyam somasthāne tu kurparam
bhalvātamukhyabhāge tu śalākām ca vidur budhāḥ
- 9.38 nāgastho maṇibandhas tu vāyoḥ karam udāhṛtam
rudradāsāṅgulī jñeyā pañcasamkhyā nakhās tathā
- 9.39 rājyakṣapade caiva bhāgād bhāgavibhāgaśaḥ
brahmādīśe tu yaḥ sandhir hṛdayam taṃ vijānataḥ
- 9.40 hṛtsandher vāmadakṣe tu stanau dvau parikalpayet
marīcasya padaike tu stanaṃ vāmam udāhṛtam
- 9.41 dharādharapadaike tu stanaṃ dakṣiṇam ucyate
marīcasya yac cheṣaṃ vai bhūtasamkhyāpadaṃ priye
- 9.42 vāmapārśvam gataṃ tatra dakṣiṇam tu dharātmakam
bhūtasamkhyāpadair yuktaḥ pārśvaś caiva varānane

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 38a stho] em.; sthe BC; sthāḥ A 39a yakṣa] conj.; yakṣmā ABC
39b vibhāgaśaḥ] AC; vibhāga[[ta]]śaḥ B
39c brahmādīśe] A; brahmādīśai BC
• sandhir] C; sandhiḥ B; sandhi A
40c marīcasya] A; sarīrasya B; śarīrasya C • padaike] BC; padeke A
41a padaike] BC; padeke A 41b stanaṃ] BC; stana A
41c marīcasya] AB; śarīrasya C 42a pārśvam] em.; pārśva BC; pārśve A
42d pārśvaś] BC; pārśveś A

- 9.43 brahmaṇo 'nte tu jaṭharaṃ jaṭharānte nābhir ucyate
nābher ūrdhvādhaḥ sīmas tu tadgrahāt padaturyavat C f38r
- 9.44 kukṣi vāmaṃ vijānīyād dakṣiṇaṃ tadvad eva hi
indraīndrajayābhyāṃ tu bhāgārdhārdhabhājite A f75r
- 9.45 kaṭyādaḥ pāyurantāś ca kalpanīyā vipaścite
indrādho 'rdhe tu muṣkaṃ vai kaṭyārdhārdhaṃ prakīrtitam B f66v
- 9.46 kaṭyādhaḥ sandhikūpaṃ tu vṛṣaṇau sandhipakṣagau
sandher adho 'rdhārdhaśīśnaṃ śīśnādhaḥ pāyur ucyate
- 9.47 vṛṣaṇau pakṣagau devi sphicau tau tu vijānataḥ
vivasvatṣatpade caiva ūruś caiva vidur budhāḥ
- 9.48 pūṣādho jānur uddiṣṭaṃ jānvādho jaṅgha ucyate
vitathādaḥ samārabhya yāvad gandharvagocare

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

43c ūrdhvādhaḥ] AB; ūrdhvādho C

43cd sīmas tu tad] em.; śīmastutad A; mīśastudad B; dūśastudur C

44b hi] BC; hiḥ A

46a kaṭyādhaḥ] A; kaṭyādha BC

46c adho 'rdhārdha] AB; adhodhvārdha C

• śīśnaṃ] C; śīṣnaṃ B; śīṣna A 46d śīśnādhaḥ] C; śīṣnādhaḥ AB

47c vivasvat] em.; vivasvā AB; vivasvān C • pade] A; padai B; padaiś C

47d ūruś] AB; rudraś C 48a pūṣādho] C; pūṣādha B; pūṣā vai A

• uddiṣṭaṃ] AC; udiṣṭaṃ B 48b jaṅgha] C; jaṅghar AB

- 9.49 jaṅghāpārśve bhaved dairghyaṃ jaṅghādho 'rdhaṃ tu gulphakam tadadhaḥ pārṣṇikaṃ caiva tasyārdhārdhapadaṃ viduḥ
- 9.50 pādārdhārdhāṅgulīnāṃ tu aṅgulyārdhārdhato nakhāḥ vāmajaṅghā samuddiṣṭā dakṣiṇoru kalādhīpaḥ
- 9.51 ṣaṭpadaiva tu bodhavyaṃ jānukaṃ rogasamjñake śoṣādau sragdvijāntāś ca jaṅghaiṣā ca prakīrtitā
- 9.52 sugrīvārdhe tu gulphaṃ vai pārṣṇī cāparārdhataḥ tasyārdhārdhapadaṃ proktaṃ pādādho 'rdhāṅgulī bhavet
- 9.53 pitaro 'rdhe nakhāḥ proktāḥ pūrvavad varavarṇini brahmātmage pṛṣṭhe pṛṣṭhamarma udāhṛtaḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

49a pārśve] em.; pārśva ABC

49b jaṅghādho 'rdhaṃ] AB; jaṅghādhordhvaṃ C

49d tasyārdhārdha] CB; tasyārdhārdhā A

50a pādārdhārdhāṅgulīnāṃ] AC; pādārdhārdhāṅgulīnān B

50b nakhāḥ] A; nakhā BC

50d dakṣiṇoru kalādhīpaḥ A; dakṣiṇokalalādhīpaḥ B; dakṣiṇākalalodhīpaḥ C

51a padaiva] AB; padai{va} C

51d prakīrtitā] C; prakīrtitāḥ AB 52b pārṣṇī] A; pārṣṇīm BC

• cāparārdhataḥ] AB; caparārdhataḥ C

52c tasyārdhārdha] AB; tasyārdhordhva C

52d 'rdhāṅgulī] AC; rddhāṅgulīm B

53a nakhāḥ] A; nakhā{ḥ} C; nakhā B

• proktāḥ] BC; prokta A

53b pūrvavad] BC; pūrvavat A

• varavarṇini] BC; varṇini A

- 9.54 adhomukho na marma vai jñātavyaṃ surasundari
hr̥tsandhipr̥ṣṭhadeśe tu hr̥dy antaṃ tu vidur budhāḥ
- 9.55 vaṃśā yaḥ sandhayaḥ pr̥ṣṭhe marma taṃ tu kṛkātīkā
indraīndrajayaḥ pr̥ṣṭhe trikaṭaṃ taṃ na saṃśayaḥ
- 9.56 adhomukho yadā vāstuḥ prāsādādyāgrhādiṣu
tadā niveśanaṃ kuryān marme marma na pīḍyate
- 9.57 uttānaṃ pūjanārthe tu śalyoddhāraṃ ca nānyathā
yathā vāstus tathā marma tanmadhye sūtrasandhigam
- 9.58ab sampātaṃ tad bhaven marma moktavyaṃ tu prayatnataḥ
piṅgalovāca
- 9.58cd marmapīḍā prakartavyā yadi deva tadā katham
- 9.59 yad vāstukaḥpanaṃ proktaṃ tat kṣetrasya parigrahaḥ
kṣetre kuḍyādivinyāsaḥ kāryo deva grhādiṣu
- 9.60 kathaṃ tad yujyate kartur yato marmamayo hi saḥ
yathā vāstus tathā marma tasmād vāstur na yujyate

A f75v

Ω = AB(→C)

- 54a mukho] B; mukhe AC • marma] A; marmaṃ BC
54d hr̥dy] em.; hr̥ty ABC
56a mukho] BC; mukhe A 56b grhādiṣu] BC; grhādiṣuḥ A
56c kuryān] BC; kuryāt A
56d marma] A; marmaṃ BC • pīḍyate] A; pīḍayet BC
57c marma] AB; marmas C
58a sampātaṃ] AB; sampāntaṃ C • tad] BC; tat A • bhaven] C; bhavet AB
58b prayatnataḥ] AC; prayatnayaḥ B
59d grhādiṣu] BC; grhādiṣuḥ A
60a yujyate] AB; ktate C • kartur] BC; kartuṃ A
60b marmamayo] AC; marmayo B
60c vāstus] C; vāstu AB • marma] AB; marmas C

- 9.61 bahiś cet kriyate 'raṃbhas tadā vai nirahetukaḥ
tasmāt sarvaprayatnena marmād evārcanaṃ kuru B f67r
- 9.62 śalyoddhāraṃ ca deveśa kriyate tat kathaṃ vai vai
vāstuṃ prati yathā pūjā kriyā kāle baliṃ vada

bhairava uvāca
- 9.63 saṃniveśanakāle tu prāsādānāṃ sureśvari
caturaśraṃ vṛttaṃ tryaśraṃ yadrūpaṃ vāstu kīrtitam
- 9.64 iṣat tac ceśato nītvā rakṣoghnārthe sureśvari
samantāc cālayed vāstuṃ vidhinānena sundari
- 9.65 vāstau saṃcalite naiva marmādyāṃ calitaṃ bhavet
evaṃ sandhyādīmarmāṇāṃ madhyān madhyaṃ tu vañcanam
- 9.66 caturaśrādyam ārambhaṃ vidhānena prakalpayet
bhittyārambhe tu deveśi prakārādyāṃ śṛṇuṣva me

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

61a 'raṃbhas] C; 'rambhaḥ AB

61d evārcanaṃ] A; evāṃrcanaṃ B; evāṃcārcanaṃ C • kuru] BC; kuruḥ A

62b tat kathaṃ] AB; tatvārthaṃ C • vai vai] AC; vaiḥvaiḥ B

before 63a uvāca] BC; uvā A

63c tryaśraṃ] AB; tryaṃśaṃ C

64a iṣat] B; iṣat C; īśat A

64b ghnārthe] conj.; ghnārdha ABC

64c vāstuṃ] BC; vāstu A

65a vāstau] em.; vāstuṃ A; vāstu BC • saṃcalite] BC; saṃcalitaṃ A

66b prakalpayet] C; kalpayet AB

- 9.67 yat kiṃ cid bhittimānaṃ tu tilārdhā hīnavādhikam
kṛtvā saṃkalpayed bhittiḥ saṃśayaṃ nātra kārayet
- 9.68 evaṃ kriyate yad vāmaṃ dr̥ṣṭādr̥ṣṭaṃ phalāvaham
śalyoddhāraṃ pravakṣyāmi yathāvat tat tathā śṛṇu
- 9.69 samyak śalyavidācāryaḥ samyag vāstuvīdhānavit
ādau tu manasā kalpya vāstuṃ caiva sureśvari
- 9.70 supracchane sugupte ca vijane kaṭaveṣṭite
śākuniśakunair devi śalyoddharaṇam ācaret
- 9.71 divyādivyavimīśraṃ ca trividhaṃ taṃ vidur budhāḥ
devādidarśanaṃ divyam adivyaṃ mānuṣātmakam
- 9.72 śvānolūkakakākādyāṃ vimīśraṃ taṃ na saṃśayaḥ
sāttvikaḥ karttur ācāryaḥ śreṣṭhaṃ devādidarśanam

C f38v

 $\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

68a vāmaṃ] vāma A; vāsa BC

68b dr̥ṣṭādr̥ṣṭaṃ] em.; dr̥ṣṭādr̥ṣṭa A; dr̥ṣṭvādr̥ṣṭa C; dr̥ṣṭādr̥ B

70d ācaret] AB; ā{care}t C

71c divyam] AC; divya B

72a śvānolūkakakākādyāṃ] BC; śvānolūkakakākādyāṃ A

- 9.73 rājasaḥ kartur ācāryo jñeyaṃ miśraṃ tu madhyamam
tāmasaḥ kartur ācāryaḥ kanyasaṃ mānuṣātmakam
- 9.74 evaṃ jñātvā tu śakunam uddharec chalyavit sadā
vikṛtiṃ saṃpravakṣyāmi nagarātmani yathā bhavet
- 9.75 kartāram ānayet tatra yatrāsau vāstuḥ kalpitaḥ
āgate tatra kartāraṃ suvijño gurur lakṣayet
- 9.76 śiraḥ sthitvā śiraḥkaṇḍūḥ kurute kārako yadā
śiraḥśalyaṃ tathā tasmin uddharet tatpramānataḥ A f76r
- 9.77 mukhe sthitvā mukhe kaṇḍūṃ kṛtvā śalyaṃ tu kāṣṭhakam
dvihastād uddharet tatra grīvasthe grīvadarśanāt B f67v
- 9.78ab lohaśṛṅkhalaṃ tatrasthaṃ mānena trikareṇa tu

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

75b vāstuḥ] em.; vāstu ABC

• kalpitaḥ] BC; kalpitāḥ A

75c kartāraṃ] em.; kartāraḥ C; karttāro AB

• gurur] AC; guru B

77a mukhe kaṇḍūṃ] BC; mukhaḥkaṇḍūṃ A

77d darśanāt] C; syarśanāt AB

78a śṛṅkhalaṃ] C; śṛṅkhala AB

- 9.78cd udarastho yadā kartā spr̥śate codarātmani
- 9.79 paśuśalyaṃ bhavet tatra sārdhahastadvayena tu
haste hastau kṛtau kṛtvā khaṭvā pādau samādiśet
- 9.80 dvātriṃśatyaṅgulaṃ khatvā tatroddhāryaṃ vipaścite
bāhau sthitvā yadā bāhuvikāraṃ kurute 'tmani
- 9.81 tanmūlaṃ tatra śalyaṃ tu cinmātra uddharet sadā
evaṃ vāme vinirdiṣṭaṃ dakṣiṇe kaṭimātrataḥ
- 9.82 tac chalyaṃ tatra nirdeśyaṃ kapālaṃ vā mṛdātmaakam
kaṭisthe tu kaṭiḥ kaṇḍūṃ yadā karoti kārakaḥ
- 9.83 dvihastād uddharet tatra kīlakaṃ lohanirmitam
ūrusthaś corusaṃsparśāt sārakāṣṭhaṃ ca tatra vai
- 9.84ab sārdhahastaṃ khanitvādhas tac chalyaṃ tu viśodhayet

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 78d codarātmani] BC; cātmarātmaṇi A
- 80a triṃśaty] em.; triṃśatty ABC
- khatvā] AB; khaṭvā C
- 80b tatroddhāryam] AB; tatroddhāraṃ C
- 80c bāhu] em.; bāhur ABC
- 80d kurute 'tmani] AB; kurutaātmani C
- 81b cin] C; vin AB
- mātra uddharet] C; mātroduddharet AB
- 82a nirdeśyaṃ] C; nirdiśyaṃ AB
- 83c ūru] AC; ūrū B
- 83d kāṣṭhaṃ] C; kāṣṭhañ B; kāṇṭhaṃ A
- vai] BC; vaiḥ A

9.84cd jānustho vikṛtau jāte śalyaṃ sthūṇātmakaṃ viduḥ

9.85 nāpitopaskaro vātha hastamātrāt samuddharet
gulphasthe gulphasamsparsād dhayapādaṃ vinirdiśet

9.86 daśāṣṭāṅgulamānena tatra khatvā samuddharet
pādashṭhaḥ pādasaṃsparsād ibhāsthim tatra cādiśet

9.87 tālamātrādhataḥ khatvā uddharet vicakṣaṇaḥ
pitṛstho 'ṅguṣṭhasaṃsparsāt khaṭī barhiṇacitritā

9.88 śalyaṃ proktaṃ tad uddhāryaṃ dviraṣṭāṅgulamānataḥ
pitarastho 'thavā devi kaniṣṭhāvikṛto yadā

9.89 kāṃsyātmakaṃ tadā śalyaṃ uddhāryāṣṭāṅgulena tu
pādasthas tu yadā kartā pādādhaḥ sprśate priye

9.90ab carmaśalyaṃ tadā tatra uddhāryāṣṭāṅgulena tu

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

84d sthūṇātmakaṃ] C; sthūnātmakaṃ AB

85d vinirdiśet] A; cavinirdiśet B; canirdiśet C

86b khatvā] A; khaṭvā B; khaṭvām C

86c sthaḥ] A; stha B; sthaṃ C

86d cādiśet] AB; vādiśet C

87a khatvā] BC; khaṭvām C

87c pitṛstho 'ṅguṣṭha] AB; pitṛsthāṃguṣṭa C

87d khaṭī] conj.; khetī AB; khetā C • citritā] BC; citritāḥ A

88c pitara] AB; pitaraḥ C

9.90cd urastha urasaṃsparśād dhṛc chalyaṃ tatra vādiśet

9.91 adho rudrāṅgulaṃ khatvā uddharen nātra saṃśayaḥ
pārśvastho vikṛte jāte śalyaṃ pāṃsulikātmakam

9.92 tasmin sthāne samuddhāryaṃ narārdhāt kathitam tava
kucasthas tu yadā bhadre kucam sprśati kārakaḥ

9.93 mārjārapañjaraṃ tatra kucamānāt samuddharet
brahmasthaḥ pṛṣṭhasaṃsparśād bhaved vārāhakurparam

A f76v; B f68r

9.94 tatra vetvā samuddhāryaṃ nābhimātrān na saṃśayaḥ
īśasthaś cakṣusaṃsparśāt tanmānān mauktikaṃ bhavet

9.95 śrutisthaḥ śrutisaṃsparśāt pravālam vātha kāñcanam
rajataṃ ca śubhā hy ete kaṇṇamātrāt samuddharet

9.96 pratyayārthaṃ tad uddhāryaṃ mauktikādyam sureśvari
punaḥ saṃsthāpayet tatra dravyaṃ cānyavimiśrikam

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

90c stha] C; sthaḥ AB

90c saṃsparśād] BC; saṃsparśāt A

90d dhṛc] BC; hṛc A

91a khatvā] AB; khatvā C

91c stho] AB; sthe C

91d pāṃśu] AC; pāśu B

92b tava] C; tavaḥ AB

94d mānān] AC; mānāt B

95b kāñcanam] BC; kāṃcanaḥ A

96b mauktikādyam] AC; mottikādyā B

96c tatra] AC; atra B

96d cānya] AB; cānya{d} C

• vimiśritam] BC; visiśritam A

- 9.97 sphicau sthitvā spr̥ṣet taṃ tu trapuṃ tatra vinirdīset
kaṭimātrādhaḥ khatvā ca uddhareta varānane
- 9.98 vaktrasthaś ca spr̥ṣed dantān tatrābhṛakakapālakam
trihastaparimāṇena khatvā samyak samuddharet
- 9.99 bhruvoḥ saṃsparśanād bhadre kācaśalyaṃ trihastakam
kakṣau kakṣākṛtiṃ vindyāt kṛṣṇalohaṃ karatrayāt
- 9.100 śīśne tu vikṛtiṃ yāte trilohaṃ tatra jāyate
trikarādhaḥ samuddhāryam iti śāstrasya niścayaḥ
- 9.101 athavā vāstumadhye tu sthitvā vaikārakottamaḥ
yadādhunātisarvāṅgaṃ tadā śalyaṃ samantataḥ
- 9.102 tad uktaṃ pūrvaśalyaṃ tu sthāne sthāne vijānataḥ
sikatāsmāṅgāralohāsthituṣakharparakīlakāḥ

C f39r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

97cd ca uddhareta] conj.; coddhareta ABC

98a dantān] B; daṃtāṃs A; dantā C

98c parimāṇena] AC; parimāṇe B

98d khatvā] AB; kh{ā}tvā C

99b hastakam] AC; hakaṃ B

102c sikatāsmāṅgāra] em.; sikatāsmāṅgāra A; sikatāmmaṅgāra B;
sikatāmaṅgāra C

- 9.103 ghoṣatārā ca kanakaṃ pravālo maṇi mauktikaḥ
sarvaṃ śalyair yataḥ kīrṇas tataḥ saṃkīrṇa ucyate
- 9.104 naramātrādhaḥ khanitvā śodhitavyaṃ prayatnataḥ
śodhyaitān kīrṇaśalyān tu pūrayet prāgvidhānataḥ
- 9.105 śuddho vai jāyate vāstus tataḥ sūtrādikalpanā
marmādeḥ kalpanāṃ kṛtvā devānāṃ sthāpanaṃ priye
- 9.106 vāstu sampūjayitvā tu tatpater balim āharet
brahmādyāḥ patayaḥ proktā grahādyās ca sureśvari
- 9.107 yathā teṣāṃ baliḥ proktaḥ tathā samyag nibodha me
ghṛtadhāreśadevāya parjanya vē kṣataṃ dadet
- 9.108 kajakaṃ jayadevāya māhendrāya śṛṇu priye
vajayantī ca pītā ca paryāyaṃ dhvajam ucyate

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

between pravā and maṇi, BC repeats a portion from 99d -100d:

lohaṃ karatrayāt

śiśne tu vikṛtiṃ yāte trilohaṃ tatra jāyate

trikarādhaḥ samuddhāryam iti

The error probably arose when a scribe's eye jumped from the –lo of pravālo to the lo- of loha. At B the insert is bracketed for removal. At C it is not.

103a ca] BC; ra A

103b mauktikaḥ] BC; mauktikaṃ A

104c śodhyaitān] BC; śodhyetāṃ A

105a vāstu] em.; vāstum ABC

105c kalpanāṃ] A; kalpanaṃ BC

106b pater] em.; patphar AB; patpur C

107a proktaḥ] AB; proktas C

107c ghṛtadhāreśadevāya] em.; ghṛtadhāresadevāya ABC

107d parjanya vē] BC; parjanya A

108d paryāyaṃ]AB; paryāya C • dhvajam] AB; dhvagam C

- 9.109 suvarṇodakam sūryāya satyāya ca punaḥ śṛṇu
dhūmraṃ vitānakam caiva dātavyam hitam icchatā
- 9.110 ghr̥takṣīrasamāyuktaṃ caruṃ godhūmajam priye
bhṛśāya sampradātavyam yadīcchet siddhim ātmanaḥ
- 9.111 mīnaṃ tad antarikṣāya svinnaṃ māṃsam athāpi vā
vahner baliṃ pravakṣyāmi śṛṇuṣv ekāgramānasā
- 9.112 śaktavo ghr̥tamākṣīkākṣīrayuk śucipūritam
śruveṇa sahasam yukte dātavyam śāntim icchatā
- 9.113 jvālā pūṣṇe ca dātavyā baliṃ caiva sureśvari
vitathāya pradātavyam ratnavāri suniścayaḥ
- 9.114 gr̥hakṣatāya dātavyam madhuṃ suravarārcite
matsyamāmsam pradātavyam yamadevāya suvrate
- 9.115 candanādīkagandham ca gandharvāya nivedayet
dviyajihvā pradātavyā bhṛṅgadevāya sarvadā

B f68v
A f77r

Ω = AB(→C)

- 109a suvarṇodakam] C; suvarṇodaka AB
110d yadīcchet] AC; y[[ā]]adīcchet B
111a antarikṣāya] AB; antarīkṣāya C
111b svinnaṃ] A; svinam B; svīna C
111d ekāgramānasā] AC; ekāgramānasaḥ B
112b śuci] em.; suci ABC • pūritam] BC; pūjitam A
112c śruveṇa] AB; sruveṇa C
113a jvālā] BC; jvālāḥ A • baliṃ] BC; baliś A
115a gandham ca] BC; gandhamśce A
115c pradātavyā] BC; pradātavyām A

- 9.116 samūlaṃ yavavṛkṣaṃ tu mṛgāya pratipādayet
kṛsaraṃ kravyasaṃyuktaṃ piṭṛsaṃjñasya dāpayet
- 9.117 dvauvārikāya dātavyaṃ kāṣṭhaṃ dantaviśodhanam
sugrīve pūpakaṃ dadyāt kuśaṃ dayāt tu śragdvije
- 9.118 pracetase pradātavyaṃ rājīvaṃ padmam ucyate
asure tu surā deyā ghṛtānnaṃ śośadevate
- 9.119 rogendrāya pradātavyaṃ maṇḍakaṃ varavarṇini
dhvajam pītaṃ daded vāyor nirvighnaṃ nānyathā priye
- 9.120 phaṇīndrāya pradātavyaṃ puṣpaṃ vai nāgakeśaram
sumukhye phalajātiṃ tu drākṣaṃ cāmṛādim eva vā
- 9.121 bhaktasūpaṃ pradātavyaṃ bhalvāṭe nātra saṃśayaḥ
madhughṛtasamāyuktaṃ some bhaktaṃ pradāpayet
- 9.122 piṭṛdevāya tatsthāne kalpyaṃ caiva sureśvari
kṣīrapayasam dātavyaṃ saghṛtaṃ madhumiśritam

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

116b mṛgāya] BC; mṛā[[ra]]ya A

118b padmam ucyate] C; padmamocyate B; padmaśocyate A

118d śośa] BC; vṛṣa A

119a pradātavyaṃ] AC; pratavyaṃ B

120b nāgakeśaram] A; nāyakesaram BC

- 9.123 balikāle yatas te tu balyarthe saṃnibandhanāḥ
kumudasya tu yat kandaṃ saugandhikam athāpi vā
- 9.124 utpalasyātha padmasya rigidevāya dāpayet
aditaye pradātavyā mullopikā sureśvari
- 9.125 purikā ditidevāya dātavyā hitam icchitā
āpavatsaṃ dadhi dadyād āpe dadyāt payaḥ priye B f69r
- 9.126 marīcaye modakaṃ syāt sāvitrai tu kuśodakam
savitreś cārghapuṣpaṃ tu dātavyaṃ varavarṇini
- 9.127 vivasve ca pradātavyaṃ raktacandanalepanam A f77v; C f39v
jayadevāya dātavyaṃ haritānnaṃ sureśvari
- 9.128 yatra saumārikaṃ grhyabhaktaṃ tadrasabhāvitam
haritānnaṃ ca tac caktaṃ kṛtrimaṃ taṃ tu tattvataḥ
- 9.129 khiccānnaṃ indradevāya guḍabhaktaṃ kalādhipe
ghṛtānnaṃ rudradāsāya rudrāya phalguṣaiḥ saha

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 123b saṃnibandhanāḥ] BC; saṃnibandhanā A
124b rigidevāya] em.; rigidevā A; giridevāya BC
125c āpavatsaṃ] BC; āpavatsa A
• dadyād] BC; dadyāt A
126a modakaṃ] BC; sādakaṃ A
126c cārgha] A; caghra BC
127a vivasve ca] AB; vivasvate C
128a yatra] BC; yatraṃ A
128d kṛtrimaṃ] BC; kṛtimaṃ A
129d saha] BC; sahaḥ A

- 9.130 pṛthivīdharāya kulmāṣaṃ matsyamāṃsasamanvitam
kecid vadanti kulmāṣaṃ sāṅkuraṃ varavarṇini
- 9.131 kecit satuṣapiṣṭaṃ tu svinnam iṅḍarikeva hi
ubhayau vā pradātavyau sāṅkuraṃ svinnam eva ca
- 9.132 yad baliṃ brahmaṇe caiva tac chṛṇuṣva samāhitā
ghṛtakṣīracaruṃ havyaṃ tilākṣatayavān kuśam
- 9.133 pañcagavyasamāyuktaṃ dātavyaṃ siddhim icchatā
ghṛtasiddhaṃ tathā kravyaṃ carukyā sampradāpayet
- 9.134 māsabhaktasamāyukto matsyamāṃsasamanvitaḥ
skandāya ca pradātavyo baliś caiva sureśvari
- 9.135 hr̥tpadmena samāyuktaṃ saghṛtaṃ māṃsam eva ca
vidārikāyai dātavyo balir evaṃ na saṃśayaḥ
- 9.136 baliś cāryamanāthāya kṛsaraṃ pūpakaiḥ saha
phalguṣeṇa samāyukto dātavyo hitam icchatā

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

- 130a pṛthivī] AC; pṛthi{vī} B • kulmāṣaṃ] BC; kulmāṣa A
130b matsya] AC; matsa B • samanvitam] BC; samanvitaḥ A
131c ubhayau] em.; ūbhayo ABC
131d sāṅkuraṃ] AB; sāṅkuraṃ C
132d tac chṛṇuṣva] BC; tatśṛṇuṣva A
133a samāyuktaṃ] BC; samāyuktaḥ A
133c siddhaṃ] AC; siddhiṃ B
133d carukyā] AB; carakyā C
134b matsya] AC; matsa B
134d baliś] AC; baliñ B
135d evaṃ] conj.; eṣā ABC
136a cāryama] AC; caṃnyama B
136b saha] BC; sahaḥ A
136d hitam] BC; hita[[kāmya]]m A

- 9.137 saraktaṃ pittamāṃsaṃ ca pūtanāyai pradāpayet
jambhakāya pradātavyaṃ sārdrāmāṃsārksaṃyuktam
- 9.138 sāsthikhaṇḍāmiṣaṃ raktaṃ pittaṃ vai pāparākṣasī
sāndraṃ raktaṃ ca kusumaṃ pilipicchāya dāpayet
- 9.139 vāstoḥ patyuh samākhyāto balir evaṃ na saṃśayaḥ
mantraṃ teṣāṃ pravakṣyāmi pūjāṃ balividhir yathā
- 9.140 caturthāntaṃ svanāma ca praṇavādivibhūṣitam
namaskārāntasaṃyuktaṃ pūjāmantras tv ayaṃ priye
- 9.141 gandhadhūpādikaṃ dadyāt svāhāntena na saṃśayaḥ
vausaḍantārghadānaṃ ca svadhānte balikarmani
- 9.142 vaṣaḍantena pānaṃ syād evamādyā vidur budhāḥ
dikpāle parito dadyād vidhinānena suvrate

B f 69v

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 137a raktaṃ] BC; raraktaṃ A
137d sārdra] AB; sārdrha C
139d balividhir] BC; balidhir A
140a nāma] C; nāmañ AB
140d mantras] AC; mantraṃs B
142a antena] A; ante[-] C; ante B
• pānaṃ] BC; pāna A
142b ādyā] AC; ādyo B

- 9.143 tathā bhūtagaṇebhyaś ca diṅmātṛñāṃ tathaiva ca
sarvān na sahitaṃ dadyād baliṃ vai sarvakāmikam
- 9.144 mantraṃ teṣāṃ pravakṣyāmi śṛṇuṣva vahitā priye
praṇavaṃ pūrvaśabdaṃ ca diśāśabdaṃ tathaiva ca
- 9.145 vāsine ca tathā likhya bhūtebhyo 'rghaḥ prakīrtitaḥ
ebhyo likhya punar devi aghorebhyo likhet kramāt
- 9.146 ghoraśabdaṃ punar likhya punar ghoratareti ca
punar bhyaś ca tataḥ sarvataḥ sarvaṃ tu punar bhavet
- 9.147 punaḥ sarvaṃ samālikhya bhyo namas tadanantaram
sa cātmane samālikhya bhyonte ca punar eva hi
- 9.148 namaḥ svāhā tathā vauṣaṭ svadhā vaṣaḍ yathā kramam
pūjādyā yānamantrās ca jātyāntā parikalpanā

Ω = AB(→C)

143b mātṛñāṃ] C; mātrīñāṃ A; mātriñāṃ B

143c dadyād] BC; dadyāt A

144b śṛṇuṣva] B; śṛṇusva A; śṛṇuṣvā C

145b 'rghaḥ] AC; ghaḥ B

145c punar] BC; purna A

146c bhyaś] AB; nyaś C

147a punaḥ sarve] em.; punasarve A; sarve B; sarve [– –] C

147b bhyo] AB; nyo C

- 9.149 hraṃ cānte tu visarjeta bhūtānāṃ vidhi coditaḥ
yatra śabdaṃ tu bhūtānāṃ māntrīṇāṃ taṃ nayo jayet
- 9.150 tāsāṃ vidhiḥ sa evoktaḥ pūrvaṃ vai yad udīritam
piṅgalovāca
grahavāstus tvayā deva prokto bhūtātmako 'pi ca
- 9.151 yathā teṣāṃ baliḥ siddhaḥ tathā kathaya me sphuṭam
bhairava uvāca
sauvarṇakaṃ kajaṃ deyaṃ sūryāyātra na saṃśayaḥ
- 9.152 some kṣīraṃ pradātavyaṃ śvetapuṣpasamanvitam
svastikaṃ raktapuṣpaṃ ca bhūsutāya pradāpayet
- 9.153 ghṛtapūrṇaṃ srajaṃ pītaṃ budhāya ca pradāpayet
dadhibhaktaṃ kuśopetaṃ gīrvāṇam avicārayet
- 9.154 phalguṣālisamopetaṃ śukrāya pratipādayet
modakotpalasaṃyuktaṃ śanau samyañ nivedayet

C f40r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

150a evoktaḥ] BC; evoktaṃ A

150b udīritam] BC; udīritaḥ A

151b me] BC; se A

152c ca] BC; tu A

154d śanau] C; śanaiḥ AB

• samyañ] C; samyag A; samyak B

- 9.155 kumudaṃ madhusaṃyuktaṃ rāhave sampradāpayet
śaktavo nīlapuṣpaṃ tu ketave sarvadā priye
- 9.156 yathā vinyāsayogena balis teṣāṃ tathā priye
śaṅkhabheryādīśabdāṃs tu vyomāya sampradāpayet
- 9.157 mṛduvastradhvaṃ vāyoḥ gṛhadīpaṃ tu pāvake
nakraṃ piṣṭamayāṃ kṛtvā varuṇāya pradāpayet
- 9.158 kūrmaḥ sāksāt pradātavyaḥ nirmaṭaḥ piṣṭakena vā
pṛthivyaiva varārohe nyāsas tu balikarmaṇi
- 9.159 teṣāṃ svanāmamantras tu yathāpūrvam udāhṛtaḥ
evaṃ sarvatra dātavyas tatsthāne tu diśābaliḥ
- 9.160 datvā baliṃ śubhāvāptir drṣṭādrṣṭaphalāvahā
nirvighnaṃ tu tadā bhadre samāptyārambhakarmasu

B f70r

$$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$$

- 155a kumudaṃ] A; kumuda BC
 156a vinyāsa] BC; vinyasa A
 157c kṛtvā] BC; [[vā]]kṛtvā A
 157d varuṇāya] BC; vāruṇāya A
 158a kūrmaḥ] C; kūrma AB
 159d baliḥ] B; baliṃ AC
 160a śubhāvāptir] AC; śubhāvāpti B
 160d karmasu] BC; [[su]]karmasu A

9.161 anyathā tu mahāvighnaṃ prakurvanti vināyakāḥ
tasmāt sarvatra dātavyo balir vai sārvakāmikaḥ

A f78v

9.162 evaṃ sādho bhavec chrayaḥ pūjābalividhānataḥ
prāsādakalpanāya syād gṛhakaḥkalpanam eva ca

iti jayadrathādhikāre piṅgalāmate navamaḥ prakaraṇaḥ

$\Omega = AB(\rightarrow C)$

162a sādho] AB; sā{dho} C

162c syād] em.; ścāt AB; ścād C

162d ca] BC; vā A

after 162 iti jayadrathādhikāre piṅgalāmate navamaḥ prakaraṇaḥ] em.;

itijayadrathādhikārepiṅgalāmatenavamaḥprakaraṇaḥ A;

itipiṅgalāmatenavamaḥprakaraṇaḥ BC